

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF IMPROVING THE WRITING SKILL OF THE SCHOOL PUPILS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

The article discusses useful methods in the writing process in teaching foreign languages. The author outlines the need for terminology used in written materials. Writing skills are a very important and difficult stage among all other language skills when learning any foreign language.

Keywords: writing skill, writing process, methods, editing, mind map.

Introduction.

At present time, most of young generations want to learn English language during their school years. The reason of wanting to learn English language is that English becomes the language of the world [1]. Therefore, they know this language gives the opportunity to look for vital information and knowledge about their curriculum from Internet. Almost 80 percent of books of world were written in English. Everyone knows all languages in the world have four skills like as reading, listening, speaking and writing. While we are improving our language skills, writing skill is the most complicated one among other skills [2]. So that what we do for improving our writing skills. Most of pupils of schools have difficulties to express their ideas in writing lack of enough word basis. That is why, it is important to pay attention of writing skills at school age.

Methodology.

Writing skill - is all about having adequate knowledge and abilities to express your thoughts and ideas in written words. For instance: several strategies and methods help pupils to improve their writing skills.

Reading books method - this is very popular method not only to improve writing skill, but also other three skills in English. Because while you are reading books about different topics you will have a chance to take new ideas for yourself about this topic and after some periods, these dates are gathered in your brain. As a result, you can make conversation with your group-mates about imaginary themes without any challenges. Structures of sentences in story or in the book that you read, help you to write worthy and interesting essay during your lesson at school.

Writing about your holiday travel method - this is an interesting method for teachers to use for their pupils at school. Because these ages pupils have suffered from many adventures of their head, but they are shy to express their experiences to their peers by written version. Because they are afraid of making mistakes while they are organizing their work about given topic at lesson. Teachers always give the same topic for all pupils to write about during lesson in these ages [3]. As a result, pupils are worried about writing worse than their classmates or expressing the same ideas about giving topics with their peers. They think that, their teacher may blame them to copy their peers' ideas about topic. So that they have challenges to express their theory. However, in these cases teacher gives different types of topics for pupils to write about something as interested.

Pupils do not have any worries to write the same ideas. Because they know, their topics are different from one to another. Therefore, they are confident to write the best one writing work for giving topic. That is why writing about your holiday travel method is an interesting for school pupils. During summer holidays all of pupils in-group visit different places with their family to have a rest. For example: some of them travel around beautiful countries and cities, other prefer to go to places near mountains, valleys and forests. Another one visits their relatives' houses that are far away from their hometown. As a result, they have suffered from different adventures and they take colorful emotions from their travels. When their teacher asks about this topic to write down they do not face up difficulties to write about their summer holidays. It is correct way for tutors to get good result in short periods from their learners.

Rewriting story method - most of teachers use this method during their lesson to progress writing skill of their pupils. If you use this method, you should give any topic for pupils to organize a story about it as a homework. Next lesson, you ask your pupils to tell their stories to their partner. In addition, you put time for them to tell their own story about given topic. After all of them have told their own stories one to another, you should put another time for them to rewrite heard story in a piece of paper. At that time, they begin to write a story by remembering a situation of story in their brain. As a result they have adaptation to express their thoughts about something by written version of words and this method help them to improve their writing skill in a short time. While you are using this method for pupils, you may organize proofreading or error checking method among pupils. After they have rewritten a heard story from their partner. It means pupils who sit down together at a desk, exchange their writing paper one to another and they should check grammar mistakes, lexical mistakes and word formation mistakes in this paper for each other. These methods help pupils to take motivation for moving forward in their next work.

If teacher wants to take, good results from middle school pupils, he or she should not be hurry to teach all writing strategies in a short time [4]. First, teachers start to give a question about lesson and they should ask pupils to write their answers for question in a piece of paper or teacher asks learners to list their answers to the question. As well as they may use mind mapping, writing sprints, freewriting and other strategies during the lesson.

Writing sprint is a quick writing session of between 5 and 30 minutes. The goal is to write as many words as possible, without stopping to edit or re-read what has been written. This tool can be useful if you are struggling with writer's block or a tendency for perfectionism that is stalling your writing practice.

Mind map involves writing down a central theme and thinking of new and related ideas which radiate out from the center. By focusing on key ideas written down in your own words and looking for connections between them, you can map knowledge in a way that will help you to better understand and retain information.

Another important step for teachers to teach writing processes for their pupils. Because knowing writing processes help pupils to organize their writing in a short time proudly.

Conclusion. Here we make conclusion that writing process is the process that involves from organizing ideas about any topic in your mind, to writing them in a piece of paper. The writing process considers these elements by allowing learners to plan their writing and create a publishable, final draft of their work, which they can be proud. So that writing process consists of some stages, they are pre-writing, drafting, revising and editing.

Pre-writing stage consists of all the work that is done before actual text production takes place. At this stage, you identify that you will write about as well as how you will write about it. This means that before you start writing, you need to know what demands are placed on your writing.

These stages and methods are very useful and important not only for teachers but also for pupils achieve their potential place in writing skill in any languages. Additionally we would like inform that *Drafting* - is a stage of writing process. In this stage, you write your ideas and theory about chosen topic, but this is not final form of your writing, you may add or remove any information your draft writing until you think your writing becomes a perfect one. *Revising* is a process in writing of rearranging, adding, or removing paragraphs, sentences, or words. Writers may revise their writing after a draft is complete or during the composing process.

Editing is a process that involves revising the content, organization, grammar, and presentation of a piece of writing. The purpose of editing is to ensure that your ideas are presented to your reader as clearly as possible. Proofreading focuses on checking for accuracy in smaller details of your work.

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